

INTEGRATION OF MEDICINE AND DIFFERENT DISCIPLINES

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Annotation The article discusses the integration of medicine and science. History of medicine, description of medicinal properties of medical works. New science networks and achievements were analyzed as a result of the integration of medicine and linguistics, medicine and music, medicine and literature, medicine and history, medicine and pedagogy. Theoretical and practical aspects of the development of music therapy, poetry therapy, medical and pedagogical education as a result of the communication of medicine and the sciences are discovered.

Key words: History of medicine, medical linguistics, medical poetry, poetry therapy, music therapy, medical units, medicine and folk-talk.

It is safe to say that in today's scientific age, great achievements have been made in many fields of science. Technological progress and the rise of human civilization made it possible to create many interdisciplinary integrations. This, in turn, did not bypass the field of linguistics and medicine, and it paved the way for the merger of these two fields. As a result of the practical use of the linguistic possibilities of the language, the study of the connection of linguistics with a number of disciplines, the fluency of the speech was clearly demonstrated. The practical importance of language was revealed as a result of the integration of linguistics with a number of disciplines. For example, linguistics and medicine, linguistics and philosophy, linguistics and psychology, linguistics and sociology, linguistics and informatics, linguistics and chemistry, linguistics and mathematics, medicine and literature, medicine and folkloristics, medicine and music are united in various branches of science. achieved scientific news. As a result, a number of fields were formed: psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, neurolinguistics, linguocultural studies, computer linguistics, mathematical linguistics, medical linguistics, medical informatics, bioinformatics, music therapy, etc[1].

The origin of modern medicine includes long historical periods and different views, and the basis of knowledge about various diseases, their treatment and prevention depends on the experience and observations of the people since ancient times.

Medicinal buds have been around since the dawn of man. "Medical activity is equal to the first man," wrote I.P. Pavlov[2]. The history of medicine goes back to the beginning of human civilization, because people have been fighting for their health since primitive times, using various remedies. Medicine has emerged as a result of thousands of years of observations and experiments passed down from generation to generation.

Based on the practical needs of a person, medical science continues to interact with many other sciences. The combination of medicine with biology, zoology, physics, and agriculture was studied in cognitive processes. In the culture of the Uzbek people, there is empirical evidence of the medicinal use of plants with healing properties, which have been cultivated in agriculture since the earliest times. Including cedar, mountain olive, desert mint, walnut, apricot, frankincense, spinach and others. It is clear from history that sedana acted as a medicine for the heart, liver and stomach. For example, the famous physician Abu Ali ibn Sino said: "I am dying, but sedana and hazorsipand(MEDICINAL PLANT) remain to heal you." The Uzbek people (all nations have their own medicinal plants) knew the useful properties of medicinal plants in ancient times and used them to treat various diseases. Sedana is called sedana in Uzbek, shuniz in Arabic, syhodonā in Persian, i.e. black grain, chernushka posevnaya in Russian, *Nigella sativa* in Latin. All sciences are embodied in the Holy Qur'an, including medicine. In "Hadith" it is said that "Sedana is a cure for all diseases except death. Sedana rubs the breadcrumbs. Stops headache and diarrhea. Sedana is very useful in diseases such as squinting of the face, sakta, difficult and depressed sleep, memory loss, dizziness and darkening of the eyes. it is said[2]. Many medicinal plants have been studied scientifically and are widely used in medicine.

Quality organization of educational processes, priority of given hygiene knowledge to the child first, and then scientific knowledge, opened the way for the combination of medicine and pedagogy. The differences in education of healthy and disabled children in educational processes and the elimination of imbalances in educational systems were identified as urgent problems that medicine and pedagogy should solve. In modern times, doctors and teachers feel the need for a theory of systematic sciences that combines medical and pedagogical applications that develop a person both physically and mentally[3,43]. In order to meet such needs, the integration of medical and pedagogical sciences took place. In the study of the general somatic structure of a person and the laws of normal life, branches of science such as biomedicine,

psychological medicine, pedagogical medicine, and medical linguistics occupy the main place.

The fact that medicine expresses the healing, healing themes, and that the field of science that relaxes the human soul, in harmony with music, is an indication of the existence of an ancient integration between these sciences. It is clear from history that medicine and music, compared to other branches and fields, have been a constant companion of man since the beginning of time. It is not difficult for us to learn this through the language of ancient monuments, mythologies and records. Originally from Greece, famous Roman physician and naturalist Galen (129-200) placed music in a special place in his treatment[4]. The famous Greek scientist Pythagoras was one of the first to emphasize the influence of music on the mental and physical development of a person. Even in the 19th century, music therapy, a combination of medicine and music, was considered and used as a treatment method in Europe. Observations revealed that doctors are considered to be more musical and creative than other professionals, and the reason for this is their constant struggle with illness and death, as well as depression. Music gives refreshment and morale not only to patients, but also to doctors who are constantly dealing with death. There are also special works created based on the integration of music and medicine, and these works are more related to the biography and practical research of the composer and the doctor. Among such works we include A. Greater's (1913-1986) "Mozart" monograph, A. Neimeir's "Music and Medicine"[5]

Music therapy is a type of therapy that involves listening to specific compositions. It is organized with the help of an individual or a group of people. Music can be played in the background in combination with other correction methods that increase the effectiveness of the effect.

The history of medicine is related to the beginning of mankind. After all, from the beginning of human existence until now, people of mankind have been fighting for their health and using various methods of treatment. The proof of our opinion is that some methods of treatment, the names of medicinal plants are given in "Avesta". In particular, "Avesta"¹ has a narrative about the origin of medicine. It says that people were taught the art of medicine by a man named Yima. They attribute this person to Prophet Noah. Avesta also contains some information about human anatomy and

¹ The first written information about the medicine of the peoples who lived in the territory of Uzbekistan in ancient times can be found in the Zoroastrian book "Avesta". uza.uz

physiology. It shows that the human body consists of the following 8 parts: bones, muscles, fat, brain, veins, blood, liver and liver, and two types of veins[7].

When talking about the history of medicine, it should be said that, along with prose medicine, poetic medicine, which gives a person aesthetic pleasure, provides spiritual perfection, provides spiritual nourishment to the human mind, and provides magical treatment to patients, has existed since ancient times. As the great doctor Abu Ali ibn Sina said, first of all, it is necessary to treat the patient with words, after treating his soul, his body should be treated. So, the commonality of medicine and poetry has existed since ancient times, and this has been proven by our great judges and poets. We know that in ancient times, many works were written in verse, and this was considered a tradition for that time. Along with many philosophical views, mathematical theorems, and geographical knowledge, medical texts were also created in the poem, which shows the compatibility of poetry with medicine as well as with a number of sciences. At this point, it should be said that the combination of medicine and poetry is not a new phenomenon.

The commonality of medicine and poetry existed in the works of our classical creators, in the wisdom of our great doctors, in the hadiths of our prophet, and since ancient times, doctors have served to help our patients to overcome diseases, and to convey the science of medicine to mankind in a simple and understandable way. As a result of the development of medical linguistics, which has matured in the field of medicine and linguistics, the linguistic features of medical units found in poetic works have been researched, the linguistic possibilities of medical units have been revealed, at the same time, the integration of medicine and poetry has resulted in the formation and development of "poetry therapy". helped man overcome many diseases.

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